

For comparison of simple and ternary complexes, it is convenient to calculate the values of mixing constants ($\log K_m$) by the equation⁹,

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - \frac{1}{2} [\log \beta_{02} + \log \beta_{20}]$$

which are 0.81, 0.72, 0.75, 0.66, 0.67 and 0.58 for [Cd-gly. prop.], [Cd- α -ala.-prop.], [Cd-L-leu.-prop.], [Cd-L-val.-prop.], [Cd-L-asp.-prop.] and [Cd-L-glut.-prop.] systems respectively, showing ternary complexes of Cd^{II} with amino acids. The trend of stabilities of complexes is L-glutamine < L-asparagine < L-valine < L-leucine < α -alanine < glycine, which might be a result of increase of side-chain of amino acids¹.

The sequence of stability constants for ternary complexes is the same as that for binary complexes.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. S. P. Banerjee, Professor and Head, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, for facilities, and University Grants Commission, Bhopal, for fellowship to one of them (K.N.).

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Formation Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of Lanthanum(III), Gadolinium(III) and Dysprosium(III) Complexes with Thioacids

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Manuscript received 24 January 1989, revised 22 November 1989
accepted 28 February 1990

IN view of the significant role of sulphur compounds, the present investigation deals with the study of formation constants and thermodynamics of rare earth metal ions with three thioacids, namely, 2-thiophene acetic acid (2-TPA), 3-thiophene acetic acid (3-TPA) and 3-(2-thienyl)acrylic acid (3-(2-TE)AA).

Experimental

The pH was recorded on a Eltop 3020 digital pH meter. All measurements were made in a thermostat maintained at the desired temperature ($\pm 0.05^\circ$). All metal salts (Sigma) used were converted to their perchlorates. The ligands (Aldrich) were of analytical grade. The formation constants and practical proton-ligand constants were obtained from the data obtained by titrating solutions containing (i) metal perchlorate solution (0.0005M) + thioacid (0.003M) + perchloric acid (0.004M), (ii) thioacid (0.003M) + perchloric acid (0.004M) and (i) perchloric acid (0.004M), maintained at a constant volume of 50 ml (in 50% dioxane-water medium) in each case, against standard potassium hydroxide solution (0.1M) at 25, 35 and 45° in a specially designed double-walled beaker. The experiments were performed in duplicate. The readings were found to be reproducible to ± 0.01 unit of pH. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.1M with sodium perchlorate solution.

Results and Discussion

The formation curves (\bar{n}_H vs pH) for the practical proton-ligand systems were found to be extended between 0 and 1 on the scale, which justifies monobasic nature of the thioacids. Three computational methods (a) interpolation and half-integral method, (b) linear plot method and (c) pointwise calculations, were used for evaluation of practical proton-ligand formation constant values (Table 1). The strength of acidity varies as

TABLE 1 - PROTON-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES*

Solvent: 50% dioxane, $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄)

Ligand	$\log K_1^H$		
	25°C	35°C	45°C
2-TPA	(a) 3.58	3.72	3.78
	(b) 3.58	3.73	3.78
	(c) 3.60	3.73	3.78
	(3.59)	(3.73)	(3.78)
3-TPA	(a) 3.74	3.79	4.15
	(b) 3.73	3.78	4.16
	(c) 3.75	3.80	4.15
	(3.74)	(3.79)	(4.15)
3-(2-TE)AA	(a) 3.79	4.14	4.38
	(b) 3.79	4.15	4.39
	(c) 3.80	4.15	4.39
	(3.79)	(4.15)	(4.39)

* (a) = Half-integral method, (b) = pointwise calculations, (c) = linear plot method; mean values in parenthesis.

2-TPA > 3-TPA > 3-(2-TE)AA. The thioacids differ in the position of RCOOH group in 2-TPA and 3-TPA and additional CH=CH grouping is present in 3-(2-TE)AA. The decrease in acidity in 3-TPA may be due to less negative inductive effect in 3-TPA as compared to 2-TPA and further decrease

TABLE 2—STEPWISE AND OVERALL METAL LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANT OF THE COMPLEXES*

 $\mu = 0.1 M (\text{NaClO}_4)$

Metal ion	Ligand	Temp. °C	log K_1	log K_2	log β_n	
La	2-TPA	25	3.30 (3.22)	2.88 (2.90)	6.18 (6.12)	
		35	3.35 (3.36)	2.90 (2.91)	6.25 (6.27)	
		45	3.45 (3.45)	2.95 (2.98)	6.40 (6.43)	
	3-TPA	25	3.00 (2.99)	2.77 (2.78)	5.77 (5.77)	
		35	3.10 (3.09)	2.80 (2.82)	5.90 (5.91)	
		45	3.65 (3.57)	3.02 (3.02)	6.67 (6.59)	
	3-(2-TE)AA	25	2.92 (2.92)	2.77 (2.83)	5.69 (5.75)	
		35	3.12 (3.13)	2.78 (2.78)	5.90 (5.91)	
		45	4.17 (4.20)	3.64 (3.63)	7.81 (7.83)	
	Gd	2-TPA	25	2.97 (3.02)	2.78 (2.76)	5.75 (5.78)
			35	3.10 (3.08)	2.80 (2.79)	5.90 (5.87)
			45	3.15 (3.13)	2.82 (2.81)	5.93 (5.94)
3-TPA		25	2.90 (2.92)	2.75 (2.74)	5.65 (5.66)	
		35	2.97 (2.96)	2.82 (2.84)	5.79 (5.80)	
		45	3.10 (3.10)	2.85 (2.86)	5.95 (5.96)	
3-(2-TE)AA		25	2.99 (2.92)	2.74 (2.78)	5.73 (5.70)	
		35	3.02 (3.00)	2.77 (2.78)	5.79 (5.78)	
		45	3.10 (3.10)	2.85 (2.86)	5.95 (5.96)	
Dy		2-TPA	25	3.07 (3.08)	2.75 (2.74)	5.82 (5.82)
			35	3.13 (3.08)	2.81 (2.81)	5.94 (5.89)
			45	3.22 (3.17)	2.82 (2.82)	6.04 (5.99)
	3-TPA	25	2.70 (2.70)	2.65 (2.65)	5.35 (5.35)	
		35	3.00 (2.98)	2.75 (2.76)	6.27 (6.44)	
		45	3.35 (3.50)	2.82 (2.82)	6.22 (6.23)	
	3-(2-TE)AA	25	3.42 (3.33)	2.80 (3.00)	6.22 (6.33)	
		35	3.64 (3.73)	2.97 (2.82)	6.61 (6.55)	
		45	4.32 (4.28)	3.57 (3.57)	7.98 (7.82)	

*Values determined by least-square method in parenthesis.

the molecule less acidic. The log K_1^H values agreed well with the literature¹ values.

The metal-ligand formation curves were obtained by plotting degree of formation of complex (\bar{n}) versus pL using the relationship derived by Irving and Rossotti². The metal-ligand formation constants were determined by Bjerrum half-integral method³ and the values were further computed by least-square method (Table 2). The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) accompanying complexation have been determined using the temperature coefficient and Gibbs Helmholtz equation (Table 3).

In the complexation of La^{III}, Gd^{III} and Dy^{III} with the thioacids, \bar{n} values vary between 0 and 2 indicating the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. The values of log K_1 and log K_2 are positive in all cases. The low values of log K_1 in case of rare earth metal ion-thioacid complexes are comparable with the acetic acid complexes, which indicates that sulphur may not be taking part in complexation with the metal ion. But slightly higher values for the thioacid complexes as compared to the acetic acid complex⁴ may be due to the presence of an aromatic ring and also due to the difference in medium. There exists the possibility of ionic bonding in the complexes. In the present investigation, the three thioacids are weak ligands. The 4f-electrons in lanthanide metal ions are effectively shielded from interaction with ligand orbitals by electrons in the 5s and 5p orbitals. Thus the possibility of hybridisation of 5d, 6s, 6p orbitals of unoccupied higher energy levels cannot be permitted due to these weak ligands⁵. This may also be justified by the linear relationship between log K_1 and e^2/r .

The data also indicate that higher temperature is favourable for the formation of complexes since log K_1 values at 45° are higher than at 35 and 25°. In terms of ligands, the formation constants of complexes with rare earth metal ions increase in the order, La > Dy > Gd. The order of stability in terms of ligands may be attributed to the basicity of the ligands involved. The thermodynamic parameters clearly indicate that the reactions are all endothermic (in confirmation with the metal-ligand formation constants). Thus the $T\Delta S$ term is larger enough to outweigh the + ΔH terms of these endothermic reactions. The ΔG° values of the complexes are more negative with increasing temperature showing that the complex formation is a spontaneous process. The positive values of ΔS° for these complex-forming reactions probably indicate that entropy is also favourable for the formation of complexes.

in 3-(2-TE)AA may be due to unsaturation present in the side aliphatic chain. The delocalisation of π -electrons further stabilises the molecule and make

TABLE 3 - THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF BINARY COMPLEXES

$\mu = 0.1 M$, Temp. = 35°

Metal ion	Ligand	ΔG_1	ΔG_2 kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG°	ΔH_1	ΔH_2 kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH°	ΔS_1	ΔS_2 JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔS°
La	2-TPA			21.99			4.03			58.31
	3-TPA			22.35			7.24			49.01
	3-(2-TE)AA			24.47			11.99			40.52
	2-TPA	19.81	17.16	36.96 (36.97)	5.08	2.22	7.30 (7.62)	47.82	48.50	96.32 (95.29)
	3-TPA	19.22	16.63	34.85 (34.85)	8.42	4.37	12.79 (15.25)	31.79	39.28	71.57 (63.63)
	3-(2-TE)AA	18.45	16.39	34.84 (34.85)	15.25	7.62	22.87 (24.64)	10.40	28.47	38.47 (33.16)
Gd	2-TPA	18.16	16.45	34.61 (34.61)	2.78	1.38	4.17 (4.38)	49.93	48.90	98.83 (98.00)
	3-TPA	17.45	16.74	34.19 (34.20)	4.37	3.65	7.62 (7.46)	41.79	44.45	86.24 (86.81)
	3-(2-TE)AA	12.69	16.27	33.96 (34.00)	3.98	1.90	5.88 (5.49)	44.50	46.65	91.15 (90.84)
Dy	2-TPA	18.16	16.57	34.73 (34.73)	2.17	2.23	4.40 (4.32)	51.89	46.54	98.43 (98.75)
	3-TPA	17.57	16.27	33.84 (33.85)	13.92	5.63	9.55 (17.16)	11.85	34.57	46.42 (54.18)
	3-(2-TE)AA	21.99	16.63	38.62 (38.62)	9.15	8.58	17.73 (12.54)	41.70	26.13	67.83 (68.44)

*Values in parenthesis have been calculated from the mean values as given in the parenthesis in Tables 1 and 2.

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Volumetric and Transport Properties of Chromium Sulphate in Aqueous Mixtures of Urea and Thiourea

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Manuscript received 27 January 1989, revised 28 December 1989, accepted 30 March 1990

THE study of ion solvation in mixed solvents has attracted the attention of large number of workers only during the last few years. It has been realised that ion solvation can be better understood in mixed solvents than in pure solvents, because the dielectric constant and viscosity of the medium can be varied to a desired value in the mixed solvents. For the study of ion-solvent interactions, water has been used extensively as

a component in mixed solvents due to its easy availability and high dielectric constant. There are various types of interactions which exist between ions in solutions, of these, solute-solvent interactions appear to be most important. The volumetric and viscosity behaviour of solutes in solution can provide information concerning solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions¹. The infinite dilution partial molar volumes are by definition, independent of solute-solute interactions, and can be used to examine solute-solvent interactions. The survey of literature shows that very little work has been done in aqueous-nonelectrolyte mixtures. The present work has therefore been carried out to learn more about solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions of chromium sulphate in aqueous mixtures of urea and thiourea.

Experimental

Chromium sulphate, urea and thiourea (all AnalaR) were used as such after drying over sulphuric acid. Freshly distilled conductivity water (sp. cond. 10⁻⁶ Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹) was used for preparing the urea-water and thiourea-water mixtures as well as standard liquid. The urea-water, thiourea-water mixtures of varying compositions as well as the solutions of chromium sulphate were made by weight and molalities were converted into molarities using the standard expression².

Densities were measured with an apparatus similar to the one reported by Ward and Millero³ and described elsewhere⁴. The apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v) were calculated from the density data